

PSYCHOLOGICAL IMPACT OF OUR NATIONAL VALUES ON THE YOUNGER GENERATION

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Abstract. *In this article, an attempt was made to thoroughly talk about the role of the psychological influence of our National Carers on the younger generation, about the importance of youth education.*

Keywords: *homeland, perfect personality, moral education, psychological impact, national value.*

ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКОЕ ВОЗДЕЙСТВИЕ НАШИХ НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ ЦЕННОСТЕЙ НА ПОДРАСТАЮЩЕЕ ПОКОЛЕНИЕ

Аннотация. *В данной статье предпринята попытка обстоятельно рассказать о роли психологического влияния наших Народных Воспитателей на подрастающее поколение, о важности воспитания молодежи.*

Ключевые слова: *родина, совершенная личность, нравственное воспитание, психологическое воздействие, национальная ценность.*

INTRODUCTION

The greatest force that leads the younger generation to perfection is books and life lessons. Educating young people in the spirit of national values we can see the future, the nation and our nationality as immortal free.

Forming a sense of loyalty to the motherland, trust in friendship, love for the family, respect for adults in honor of the little ones is an original manifestation of our national values. Giving a person knowledge only about the reality that is happening in the world, about the rules of etiquette, about the concepts of kindness and loyalty, alone will not be enough for his spiritual and moral education. Perhaps, we should achieve the formation of willpower, a sense of responsibility in it, the ability to instill in the soul a feeling of being kind and consequential to people other than the environment, work, profession, science, heart and soul, the birth of Great Goals and the ability to express their attitude to the events that are happening around them. And in order for the younger generation to grow up with these qualities in different ways: by listening to the advice and exhortations of adults, by developing their ability to draw the right conclusions from it; it is possible to achieve by various means and, most importantly, through a sincere (heartfelt) approach to the upbringing of the younger generation and tireless research.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Every nation in the world has national values that have lived for centuries and times. In educating the younger generation as spiritually harmonious, we will also undoubtedly build on national and universal values.

As the child grows up, serious changes occur in his psychic development. Because, from the same period, the child's independent activity is only slightly expanded. A school-age child has two strengths that are necessary for him to be able to be in independent activities. Firstly, it has an apparatus of movement that is subordinated to itself to some extent, and secondly, a

speech that is able to somewhat freely interact with the older people around it and with their peers.

Of great importance in the psychological development of children is the variety of needs and interests that arise in them. Because, needs and interests are the stimuli (factors) that motivate children to take this or that action. They are born with large people close to them and the need to relate to their peers. They begin to strive for a wider range of relationships, not being able to satisfy their needs with relationships in a narrow Family Circle. As a result, the circle of social attitudes and activities of children of this age is becoming more and more extensive.

RESULTS

From the point of view of psychology, habits are things close to need in their essence. In other words, as a result of the fact that different habits are repeated in a daily state, they become very absorbed in our body and become a need. Therefore, when we say to scale positive and beneficial needs in children, we understand that positive useful habits are formed in them. solid positive habits and moral qualities formed during preschool age are preserved throughout a person's life.

The fact that a person is a perfect person is determined by what his spiritual world will be. Good moral quality is the highest quality of a person. The child will learn from his family all such human qualities as being honest and fair in spirituality, blocking the path of ignorance and immorality, humanity, compassion, enlightenment, friendship, courage, Brotherhood, hospitality, purity, sympathy, dishonor, patriotism.

Also traditions, lifestyle, education, culture and traditions in the family, as well as labor create the basis for the manifestation of moral character traits of the child in the form of moral behavior, which is carried out by more adults in the family, that is, parents.

DISCUSSION

Moral behavior in a child when viewed from a psychological point of view:

- will;
- self-awareness;
- internal and external motive and motivation;
- emotional and individual feature;
- in the formation of character traits, the extreme has a great moral character.

Each child himself is a universe. Therefore, the teacher must approach according to the character of the child. In the right class, along with excellent, depressed students, there will be no such ability to study, and there will also be cheerful, resourceful children. When a child is treated with pleasure, he grows up as a necessary, mature person for society. Comparing the children of national heroes, it is necessary to develop their psychology by convincing them that in the future a brave man who loves the motherland, a master of his profession will come out of them.

Our values remaining from our ancestors knowledge of their native language reading the unique masterpieces left over from them it is an honor for everyone to benefit from them. This feeling remains invaluable as long as a person does not know how to read and write. It is important to take into account the fact that students can independently apply their theoretical knowledge in increasing their interest in knowledge. This experience has been successfully used in many schools.

When expressing an opinion about the methods of instilling national values into the minds and hearts of their youth, it should be noted separately that it was first required to be

careful with the method of rape. Because it is advisable to strain whenever possible, not to use the coercive method. Our First President I.A. Karimov said, " against an idea one can only enter into an argument, against an idea, against an idea only an opinion, against ignorance only with enlightenment." This is one of the main principles of educational work carried out in the spiritual and spiritual sphere in independent Uzbekistan.

CONCLUSIONS

Well, the ideological worldview, the education of young people in the spirit of national values is not an immediate solution, the formation of an ideological worldview, the effective use of all existing methods, forms, means of educational work in order to instill national values in the minds and hearts of young people occupies an important place in the implementation of our common goals.

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